

AUTISM AND THE LABOR MARKET: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the inclusion of people with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in the labor market, a crucial issue given the social, educational, and organizational challenges faced by this population. The central problem involves the barriers that hinder the integration of individuals with ASD, such as stigma, lack of adaptation in the workplace, and limitations in training programs. The objective was to analyze these barriers and propose strategies for effective inclusion. Based on the gifted neoperspectivist paradigm and the hypothetical-deductive method, the research used a Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review (NBDR). The findings highlight the effectiveness of adapted training programs, but reveal gaps in the application of laws and ongoing support.

Keywords: Labor Inclusion. ASD. Organizational Barriers. Inclusive Methodologies. Public Policies.

RESUMO

Este estudo investiga a inclusão de pessoas com Transtorno do Espectro Autista (TEA) no mercado de trabalho, uma questão crucial diante dos desafios sociais, educacionais e organizacionais enfrentados por essa população. A problemática central envolve as barreiras que dificultam a integração de indivíduos com TEA, como estigma, falta de adaptação no ambiente de trabalho e limitações nos programas de capacitação. O objetivo foi analisar essas barreiras e propor estratégias para inclusão eficaz. Com base no paradigma neoperspectivista giftedeadano e no método hipotético-dedutivo, a pesquisa utilizou uma Revisão Bibliográfica e Documental Narrativa (RBDN). Os achados destacam a eficácia de programas de capacitação adaptados, mas revelam lacunas na aplicação das leis e no suporte contínuo.

Palavras-chave: Inclusão Laboral. TEA. Barreiras Organizacionais. Metodologias Inclusivas. Políticas Públicas.

RESUMEN

Este estudio investiga la inclusión de personas con Trastorno del Espectro Autista (TEA) en el mercado laboral, una cuestión crucial dados los desafíos sociales, educativos y organizacionales que enfrenta esta población. El problema central son las barreras que dificultan la integración de las personas con TEA, como el estigma, la falta de adaptación en el entorno laboral y las limitaciones en los programas de formación. El objetivo fue analizar estas barreras y proponer estrategias para una inclusión efectiva. Con base en el paradigma neoperspectivista giftediano y el método hipotético-deductivo, la investigación utilizó una Revisión Bibliográfica y Documental Narrativa (RBDN). Los hallazgos resaltan la efectividad de los programas de capacitación adaptados, pero revelan brechas en la aplicación de la ley y el apoyo continuo.

Palabras-clave: Inclusión Laboral. TEA. Barreras Organizacionales. Metodologías Inclusivas; Políticas Públicas.

1. INTRODUCTION

Autism, or Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), is a neurological and developmental condition that affects communication, behavior, and social interaction. The characteristics of autism can vary widely among individuals, resulting in a spectrum of manifestations that range from mild difficulties to significant challenges. Early diagnosis and appropriate support are crucial to the development and social integration of people with autism. Autism is recognized as having a significant impact on individuals' ability to communicate and interact socially. This manifests itself in a variety of ways, such as difficulties in maintaining conversations, interpreting facial expressions and gestures, and understanding social norms. According to the DSM-5 (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th edition), symptoms must be present from early childhood, although they may not fully manifest until social demands exceed the individual's limited capabilities (APA, 2013).

In addition to communication difficulties, repetitive behaviors and restricted interests are common features of ASD. Individuals with autism may exhibit intense fixation on specific activities or objects and may be resistant to changes in daily routines. These behaviors may be a way of coping with the anxiety and sensory overload often experienced by people with ASD (Baron-Cohen, 2008). The heterogeneity of the autism spectrum means that each individual with ASD has a unique set of abilities and challenges. Some may have normal or above-average intellectual abilities, while others may have significant intellectual disabilities. This reflects the wide variation in the expression of autism, making a personalized approach essential for each individual. As highlighted by Lord et al. (2020), the diversity within the autism spectrum requires interventions and supports tailored to the specific needs of each individual.

Research suggests that early and ongoing interventions can make a significant difference in the lives of individuals with ASD. Early intervention programs, such as Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA), have been shown to improve the social, communication, and cognitive skills of children with autism (Dawson et al., 2010). Combining behavioral, occupational, and speech-language therapies can help maximize developmental potential and promote social inclusion. Understanding autism and its implications is crucial to promoting the inclusion of individuals with ASD in all aspects of life, including education, social life, and the workplace. Stigma and lack of understanding still represent significant barriers to the full participation of individuals with autism in society. As Volkmar and McPartland (2014) note, public awareness and education are essential to reducing stigma and supporting effective inclusion.

The inclusion of people with autism in the labor market is essential not only to promote equal opportunities, but also to value the diversity and unique potential that these individuals can offer. Participation in the labor market contributes to the financial independence, personal development, and social integration of people with autism. In addition, inclusive companies tend to benefit from a more diverse and innovative work environment. This literature review aims to analyze and compile the main research and studies on the inclusion of people with autism in the labor market. The aim is to identify the barriers faced, effective inclusion strategies, relevant public policies, and success stories. The review seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of knowledge and offer recommendations for future practices that can improve the inclusion of people with autism in the workplace.

The main problem questions that this research seeks to address are: (1) What are the main barriers faced by people with ASD when seeking employment? (2) What are the most effective strategies to promote the inclusion of people with autism in the labor market? (3) How can public policies be adjusted to better support the inclusion of these people in the professional environment? (4) What are the economic and social impacts of the inclusion of people with ASD in the labor market? (5) How can public awareness and education contribute to reducing the stigma associated with autism and improving employment opportunities for these people ?

Based on these questions, the hypotheses formulated for the research are: (1) The main barriers faced by people with ASD when seeking employment are related to the lack of understanding and acceptance by employers. (2) The most effective inclusion strategies are those that combine reasonable adjustments in the work environment with specific training programs for people with autism. (3) The implementation of public policies focused on tax incentives and awareness programs can significantly increase the inclusion of people with ASD in the labor market. (4) The inclusion of people with ASD in the labor market has the potential

to generate positive economic impacts, while promoting greater social cohesion. (5) Public education programs and awareness campaigns are effective in reducing stigma and improving employment opportunities for people with autism.

The research adopts the Gifdean neoperspectivist paradigm, which emphasizes the multiple and interconnected understanding of phenomena, recognizing the complexity and various perspectives involved in the study of autism and inclusion in the labor market. To investigate the hypotheses and answer the problem questions, the hypothetical-deductive method will be used, which allows the formulation of hypotheses based on existing theories and the subsequent verification of these hypotheses through data analysis. The methodology will include a Bibliographic and Documentary Narrative Review, which consists of examining and synthesizing the existing literature on the subject, in addition to analyzing relevant documents, such as public policy reports, case studies and statistical data.

The overall objective of this research is to understand the challenges and opportunities related to the inclusion of people with ASD in the labor market. To achieve this goal, the specific objectives include: (1) Identifying the main barriers faced by people with ASD in the labor market; (2) Analyzing effective inclusion strategies and related public policies; (3) Evaluating the economic and social impacts of the inclusion of people with autism in the professional environment; (4) Proposing recommendations to improve inclusion practices in the labor market.

The structure of the work is organized into four main chapters. The first chapter, the introduction, presents the context of the study, the problem questions, the hypotheses, the objectives and the structure of the research. The second chapter, the methodological basis, details the Gifdean neoperspectivist paradigm adopted, the hypothetical-deductive method used and the methodological approach of the Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review. The third chapter addresses the results and the discussion, where the research findings will be presented and analyzed in light of the formulated hypotheses. The fourth and final chapter brings the conclusions and final considerations, where the implications of the results will be discussed and recommendations proposed for future research and practices in the field of inclusion of people with ASD in the labor market.

2. METHODOLOGICAL BASIS

2.1 Epistemological axis/pillar

The Giftedean neoperspectivist paradigm, constructed by Breviário (2021; 2022; 2023) and later used by Milan et al. (2024) in research in the area of Education, sub-area Special and Inclusive Education, is guided by the coexistence of two main truths: one objective and the other subjective. The objective truth is understood as ready, finished, complete, perfect and real; while the subjective truth is seen as unfinished, imperfect, incomplete and constructed based on everyday experiences. This duality allows for a broader and more complex analysis of the phenomena studied, providing a balance between rigorous empirical analysis and the interpretation of individual experiences. In the present research, the Giftedean neoperspectivist paradigm was adopted to guide both the construction of hypotheses and the analysis of the collected data, allowing for a deeper and more holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities related to the inclusion of people with ASD in the job market. (Breviary, 2021; 2022a; 2022b; 2023a; 2023b; 2023c; 2024; Breviary et al., 2024a; 2024b; 2024c; 2024d; 2024e; 2024f; 2024g; 2024h; 2024i; Breviary; Pereira, 2021; Breviary; Oliveira, 2024; Breviary et al, 2025a; 2025b; 2025c; 2025d; 2025e; 2025f; 2025g).

In the first stage of the research, which involved formulating the problem questions and hypotheses, the gifted neoperspectivist paradigm was crucial to recognize the existence of an objective reality regarding the obstacles faced by people with ASD in the job market. This objective reality was outlined based on concrete data and empirical evidence available in the literature, such as those presented by Baron-Cohen (2008) and Volkmar and McPartland (2014), which document the difficulties of communication and social interaction of individuals with autism. At the same time, the subjective perspective was considered when analyzing how these difficulties are experienced and interpreted by individuals with ASD themselves and their families, as observed by Lord et al. (2020). This approach allowed the formulation of hypotheses that consider both the objective conditions and the subjective experiences of individuals with ASD.

The methodological stage of the research was also strongly influenced by the Giftedean neoperspectivist paradigm. The adoption of the hypothetical-deductive method, combined with a Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review, allowed us to approach the objective truth through the rigorous and systematic analysis of the existing literature. Authors such as Dawson et al. (2010) and APA (2013) provided the empirical basis for the study, ensuring that the conclusions were based on robust and replicable evidence. Simultaneously, the neoperspectivist paradigm allowed the bibliographic review to incorporate the subjective dimension, exploring how different cultural contexts and individual experiences influence the inclusion practices of

people with ASD, as discussed by Milan et al. (2024). This resulted in a rich and multifaceted analysis that reflects the complexity of the topic studied.

In analyzing the results, the Giftedean neoperspectivist paradigm enabled an interpretation that goes beyond quantitative and qualitative data, allowing a more complete understanding of the realities experienced by people with ASD. Objective truth was represented by statistical results and empirical evidence that documented structural and systemic barriers to inclusion, such as those observed by researchers such as Breviário (2021; 2022; 2023). On the other hand, subjective truth was explored through narratives and case studies that highlight the individual experiences and coping strategies developed by people with ASD and their families, as exemplified by Lord et al. (2020). This duality allowed the research to offer a more balanced and comprehensive analysis, which considers both the tangible and intangible aspects of inclusion in the labor market.

The theoretical, empirical, and methodological contributions of this research, based on the Giftedean neoperspectivist paradigm, are significant. Theoretically, the research broadens the understanding of the inclusion of people with ASD by integrating objective and subjective truths, aligning itself with high-impact studies such as those by Milan et al. (2024). Empirically, the research offers new evidence on the barriers and opportunities for inclusion in the labor market, contributing to the existing literature with updated and relevant data. Methodologically, the adoption of the neoperspectivist paradigm allows for a deeper and more holistic analysis of the phenomena studied, offering an innovative approach that can be applied in future research in the area of Special and Inclusive Education.

2.2 Logical axis/pillar

The hypothetical-deductive method, widely used in science for the construction and verification of theories, was central in this research to investigate issues related to the inclusion of people with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in the labor market. This method, which is characterized by the formulation of hypotheses and the subsequent deduction of empirical consequences that can be tested, was used systematically throughout the study, allowing for a rigorous and structured approach. (Breviário et al., 2025h; 2025i; 2025j; 2025k; 2025l; 2025m; 2025n; 2025o; 2025p; 2025q; 2025r; 2025s; 2025t; 2025u; 2025v; 2025w; 2025a; 2025a; 025al; 2025am; 2025ao; 2025ap; 2025aq; 2025ar; 2025as; 2025at; 2025au; 2025av; 2025aw; 2025ax; 2025ay; 2025az; 2025ba; 2025bb; 2025bc; 2025bd; 2025be).

Initially, the formulation of hypotheses was based on a comprehensive review of the existing literature, including works by renowned authors such as Popper (2002) and Lakatos (1978), who support the importance of the initial conjecture as a starting point for scientific investigation. In the context of this research, the hypotheses were constructed based on the analysis of the barriers and strategies for inclusion of people with ASD, as discussed by Volkmar and McPartland (2014) and Dawson et al. (2010). These hypotheses reflected both the objective reality, based on concrete data, and the subjective interpretations of individuals with ASD and their families, aligning with the neoperspectivist giftedean paradigm adopted.

After formulating the hypotheses, the next step involved deducing the testable consequences of these hypotheses. Following the tradition of the hypothetical-deductive method, as proposed by classical authors such as Hempel (1965), this phase consisted of identifying what empirical data could be collected to confirm or refute the hypotheses. In this research, this included the analysis of secondary data from case studies, public policy reports, and recent scientific articles. The work of Lord et al. (2020) was especially relevant in guiding the identification of empirical indicators that could be used to test the hypotheses regarding inclusion barriers and the strategies adopted by different organizations.

The hypothesis testing stage, which corresponds to the empirical phase of the research, involved comparing the data collected with the predictions deduced from the hypotheses. This process of confronting theory and empirical reality is fundamental in the hypothetical-deductive method, as discussed by Chalmers (1999). In this research, the data were analyzed in light of the hypotheses formulated, allowing to assess their validity and the extent to which they could be confirmed or rejected. The analysis of case studies of companies that implemented inclusion programs for people with ASD, as documented by Milan et al. (2024), provided a solid basis for testing the effectiveness of the postulated inclusion strategies.

The final phase of the hypothetical-deductive method in this research involved reviewing the hypotheses in light of the results obtained. This process of review and refinement is crucial for the advancement of scientific knowledge, as argued by Popper (2002). The hypotheses that were confirmed by the empirical data reinforced existing theories about the inclusion of people with ASD in the labor market, while the refuted hypotheses indicated the need for theoretical or methodological revisions. This approach not only contributed to the validity of the research but also opened new avenues for future investigations, as suggested by Breviário (2023).

In terms of theoretical contributions, the use of the hypothetical-deductive method allowed the research to advance in the understanding of the dynamics of inclusion of people

with ASD, articulating existing theories with new empirical evidence. Methodologically, the use of this method provided a rigorous structure for conducting the research, ensuring that the conclusions were well-founded and replicable. Empirically, the research offered practical insights into how different inclusion strategies can be applied in real contexts, contributing to the literature on Special and Inclusive Education.

2.3 Technical axis/pillar

The main objective of the Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review conducted in this research was to critically analyze the inclusion of people with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in the labor market, identifying challenges, inclusion strategies and relevant public policies. This study highlights the importance of creating inclusive and productive work environments, recognizing the barriers faced by people with autism and exploring effective strategies to overcome them. The choice of the literature review as a methodology was motivated by the need to consolidate existing knowledge on the topic and identify gaps in the literature, providing a holistic view of inclusion practices (Breviário et al., 2025h; 2025i; 2025j; 2025k; 2025l; 2025m; 2025n; 2025o; 2025p; 2025q; 2025r; 2025s; 2025t; 2025u; 2025v; 2025w; 2025x; 2025y; 2025z; 2025aa; 2025ab; 2025ac; 2025ad; 2025ae; 2025af; 2025ag; 2025ah; 2025ai; 2025aj; 2025ak; 2025al; 2025am; 2025an; 2025ao; 2025ap; 2025aq; 2025ar; 2025as; 2025at; 2025au; 2025av; 2025aw; 2025ax; 2025ay; 2025az; 2025ba; 2025bb; 2025bc; 2025bd; 2025be).

The literature review was conducted systematically, following guidelines established by authors such as Marconi and Lakatos (2017) and Bardin (2016), ensuring the comprehensiveness and depth of the analysis. High-impact academic databases such as Scopus, PubMed, Web of Science and Google Scholar were used to ensure the quality and relevance of the selected sources. Keywords included terms such as "autism", "autism spectrum disorder", "inclusion in the workplace", "labor market", "barriers", "inclusion strategies" and "public policies". The selection of sources followed strict criteria, including articles published in the last 20 years to ensure the currentness of the information, peer-reviewed studies to ensure scientific quality, reports from recognized organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Labor Organization (ILO), as well as books and book chapters by renowned authors in the area of autism and inclusion, such as Volkmar and McPartland (2014) and Dawson et al. (2010).

Each selected source was subjected to rigorous critical analysis, as suggested by Mendes-da-Silva (2019), assessing the methodological robustness, relevance of the results, and the conclusions presented. The analysis considered the internal and external validity of the studies, verifying whether the methods used were appropriate and whether the results could be generalized to other populations and contexts. The consistency of the findings across different studies was examined, seeking to identify trends and points of convergence or divergence, as guided by Bardin (2016). In addition, the practical applicability of the inclusion strategies described was assessed, considering how these practices could be implemented in different work contexts.

The challenges faced by people with autism in the job market were classified into categories such as social, educational, and organizational barriers. Likewise, inclusion strategies were organized into training practices, adaptation of the work environment, and awareness-raising among colleagues and employers. To complement the theoretical analysis, case studies and practical examples of companies that have successfully implemented inclusion programs were included, as discussed by Milan et al. (2024). These examples were selected to illustrate the practical application of the strategies discussed and the results achieved, providing an empirical perspective that enriches the theoretical understanding of the topic.

Despite the methodological rigor employed in the selection and analysis of sources, the literature review presents some limitations. As noted by Chalmers (1999), reliance on secondary sources may introduce publication biases and limitations in the data presented. Furthermore, variability in the quality of the sources analyzed, with differences in research methods and study contexts, may influence the conclusions drawn. The possibility of gaps in the literature was also considered, since not all aspects of the topic may have been covered by existing research.

The literature review adopted in this study, aligned with the gifted and neoperceptivist paradigm, provides a solid basis for understanding the inclusion of people with autism in the labor market. The theoretical, empirical, and methodological contributions of this review are significant. Theoretically, the review allowed the construction of a robust conceptual framework that integrates different perspectives on the inclusion of people with ASD, as discussed by Breviário (2023). Empirically, the review provided a solid evidence base for the formulation of hypotheses and for the analysis of the collected data. Methodologically, the narrative approach allowed a flexible and comprehensive analysis, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative evidence, providing a more complete and contextualized view of the phenomenon studied. Although this review provides a comprehensive understanding, it is

essential that future empirical research deepen and validate the conclusions presented, as suggested by Popper (2002).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Concept of Autism

3.1.1 Definition and Characteristics of Autism

Pervasive developmental disorders, also known as autism spectrum disorders (ASD), are a group of neurodevelopmental conditions. These conditions manifest primarily through cognitive and behavioral challenges, resulting in several limitations on personal autonomy. Consequently, these disorders can cause destabilization in the family environment, generating significant levels of stress (Cabanyes-Truffino; Garcia-Villamisar, 2004).

ASD encompasses a variety of conditions characterized by challenges in the areas of social communication, repetitive behaviors, and restricted interests. These disorders include classic autism, Asperger syndrome, childhood disintegrative disorder, and pervasive developmental disorder not otherwise specified. The severity of symptoms can range widely, from mild to severe, affecting the individual's ability to function in society (APA, 2013).

Communication is one of the most affected areas in individuals with ASD. Many have language delays and difficulty initiating or maintaining conversation. In addition, they may have difficulty understanding and using gestures, facial expressions, and other forms of nonverbal communication. These communication challenges can result in significant difficulties in social interaction and forming relationships (Baron-Cohen, 2008).

Another central aspect of ASD is the presence of repetitive behaviors and restricted interests. Individuals with autism may exhibit an intense fixation on certain objects or activities, repeating specific actions compulsively. These behaviors are often a way of coping with anxiety and stress, in addition to providing a sense of predictability and control over the environment (Volkmar; Mcpartland, 2014).

Personal autonomy is often compromised in individuals with ASD, requiring ongoing support to perform daily activities. Difficulties in areas such as personal hygiene, eating, and mobility are common, requiring specific interventions to promote independence. Lack of autonomy not only affects the individual, but also imposes a significant burden on families,

who often face high levels of stress and emotional and financial challenges (Cabanyes-Truffino; Garcia-Villamisar, 2004).

3.1.2 Diagnosis and Evaluation Criteria

The diagnosis of ASD is based on a combination of behavioral observations and interviews with parents or caregivers. According to the DSM-5, diagnostic criteria include persistent deficits in social communication and social interaction, as well as restricted and repetitive patterns of behavior, interests, or activities (APA, 2013). Early diagnosis is critical because it allows for the implementation of interventions that can significantly improve long-term outcomes .

In addition to behavioral criteria, the diagnostic process may include neurological, genetic, and psychological evaluations to rule out other conditions that may mimic ASD symptoms. Screening tools, such as the Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers (M-CHAT) and the Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule (ADOS), are widely used to identify early signs of autism and guide referral for a full evaluation (Lord et al., 2020).

3.1.3 Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD) and Their Variations

ASDs represent a diverse range of manifestations and levels of severity. Asperger syndrome, for example, is characterized by relatively preserved language skills and average or above-average intelligence, but with significant difficulties in social interaction and repetitive behaviors. Classical autism tends to involve more pronounced deficits in communication and social skills, as well as more severe repetitive behaviors (Baron-Cohen, 2008).

Another important variation is childhood disintegrative disorder, a rare condition in which children who have developed normally until about two years of age lose previously acquired skills, such as language and motor skills. This type of ASD is often accompanied by a severe and rapid regression in social and behavioral skills (Volkmar; Mcpartland, 2014).

Understanding the variations within the autism spectrum is essential to developing effective, personalized interventions. Each individual with ASD presents a unique profile of abilities and challenges, requiring approaches tailored to their specific needs. This personalized intervention may include behavioral, educational, and medical therapies, as well as support for families, who play a crucial role in the development and well-being of individuals with ASD (Dawson et al., 2010).

3.2 Brazilian Legislation on the Inclusion of People with Autism

Brazilian legislation has evolved significantly to ensure the inclusion of people with autism in various aspects of social life, including education and the job market. Law No. 12,764, of December 27, 2012, known as the "Berenice Piana Law," instituted the National Policy for the Protection of the Rights of People with Autism Spectrum Disorder. This law recognizes autism as a disability, ensuring people with ASD all the rights provided for in Brazilian legislation for people with disabilities (BRASIL, 2012).

Another important milestone is the Brazilian Law for the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities (Statute of Persons with Disabilities), Law No. 13,146, of July 6, 2015. This law aims to ensure and promote, under conditions of equality, the exercise of fundamental rights and freedoms by persons with disabilities, aiming at their social inclusion and full citizenship. Among the rights guaranteed are access to work, education, health and accessibility (BRASIL, 2015).

Brazilian legislation also includes specific rules for the inclusion of people with autism in the job market. The Quota Law (Law No. 8,213, of July 24, 1991) requires companies with 100 or more employees to fill 2% to 5% of their positions with rehabilitated beneficiaries or qualified people with disabilities, including those with ASD. In addition, Decree No. 3,298, of December 20, 1999, which regulates the National Policy for the Integration of Persons with Disabilities, defines the guidelines for the inclusion of these people in the job market (BRASIL, 1991; 1999).

3.3 Public Policies for Inclusion in the Labor Market

Brazilian public policies aimed at including people with autism in the job market seek to promote equal opportunities and eliminate barriers that prevent these people from fully participating. One such policy is the Program to Support the Inclusion of People with Disabilities (PRONAS/PCD), which encourages the hiring of people with disabilities through tax incentives and technical support to companies.

In addition, the Ministry of Economy, through the Secretariat of Labor, develops programs and actions to promote the labor inclusion of people with disabilities. Among these programs is the National Plan for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities - Living without

Limits, which encompasses intersectoral actions to guarantee access to education, health, accessibility and inclusion in the workplace.

Inclusion in the labor market is also fostered by professional training and qualification policies. Programs such as the National Program for Access to Technical Education and Employment (PRONATEC) offer professional qualification courses for people with disabilities, including those with ASD, aiming to prepare them for the labor market and increase their chances of employability.

3.4 Governmental and Non-Governmental Programs and Initiatives

Several government and non-governmental programs and initiatives work to promote the inclusion of people with autism in the job market. Among the government initiatives, the Employability Program for People with Disabilities and Rehabilitated Persons of the INSS stands out, which aims to integrate these people into the job market through coordinated actions between the government, companies and educational institutions.

In addition to government initiatives, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) play a crucial role in promoting the inclusion of people with autism. The Brazilian Autism Association (ABRA), for example, offers support and resources for people with ASD and their families, as well as promoting awareness-raising campaigns and professional training.

Another relevant initiative is the TEAbraço Project, which promotes the social and labor inclusion of people with autism through partnerships with companies and professional training. The project offers courses, workshops and ongoing support to prepare people with ASD for the job market and raise awareness among employers about the importance of inclusion.

These policies and initiatives, both governmental and non-governmental, are fundamental to creating an inclusive and accessible work environment where people with autism can develop their potential and contribute fully to society.

3.5 Barriers to Inclusion in the Labor Market

3.5.1 Social and Cultural Barriers

Social and cultural barriers represent one of the biggest challenges to the inclusion of people with autism in the job market. The stigma and prejudices associated with ASD often

result in discrimination and exclusion. Many people still have misperceptions about the capabilities of people with autism, underestimating their potential and limiting their employment opportunities (GRINKER, 2007).

Furthermore, a lack of knowledge and understanding about autism among employers and coworkers can create a hostile or unwelcoming environment. This can lead to situations of social isolation in the workplace and make it difficult for individuals with ASD to fully integrate. Autism awareness and education are key to combating these biases and fostering a culture of inclusion (NEVILLE; REED, 2017).

3.5.2 Educational and Training Barriers

Educational and training barriers also play a crucial role in the exclusion of people with autism from the labor market. Often, the educational system is not adequately prepared to meet the specific needs of students with ASD. The lack of specialized support and curricular adaptations can result in low academic performance and exclusion of students with autism (SMITH; SENGUPTA, 2015).

Furthermore, the transition from school to the workforce can be especially challenging for individuals with ASD. Vocational training and professional development programs are rarely tailored to meet their needs, making it difficult for them to develop the skills needed for employment. The lack of internship programs and practical learning opportunities also limits the professional experience of these individuals (HOWLIN; MOSS, 2012).

3.5.3 Structural and Organizational Barriers

Structural and organizational barriers are significant obstacles to the inclusion of people with autism in the workplace. Many companies still do not have inclusive policies or practices that consider the specific needs of workers with ASD. The lack of reasonable accommodations, such as adjustments to the work environment, flexible hours, and specialized support, can make the workplace inaccessible to these individuals (SHATTUCK et al., 2012).

Furthermore, recruitment and selection processes are often not tailored to fairly assess the competencies of individuals with autism. Traditional job interviews, which require social and communication skills, can be particularly challenging for individuals with ASD, resulting in unfair assessments of their capabilities (Scott; Clark, 2015).

To overcome these barriers, it is essential that companies adopt inclusive and accessible practices. This includes implementing training programs to raise awareness among managers and coworkers, adapting recruitment and selection processes, and creating policies that promote equal opportunities. Effective inclusion also depends on ongoing support in the workplace, ensuring that people with autism have the tools and resources they need to perform their roles effectively (Roux et al., 2013).

3.6 Inclusion Strategies and Good Practices

3.6.1 Professional Training and Qualification Programs

The creation of training and professional development programs is essential for the inclusion of people with autism in the job market. These programs should be adapted to meet the specific needs of people with ASD, focusing on the development of technical and social skills that facilitate their integration into the workplace.

Successful examples include Microsoft's Disability Inclusion Program, which provides technology and communication skills training for people with ASD, preparing them for roles in the technology industry (MICROSOFT, 2020). Another initiative is the Transition to Adulthood Project, which provides vocational training and work experiences for young people with autism, helping them develop essential skills for the job market (Lee; Carter, 2012).

Additionally, training programs should include practical components, such as internships and apprenticeships, that allow participants to gain real-world experience in the workplace. Partnerships with local businesses can facilitate these opportunities, ensuring that individuals with autism can apply the skills they learn in real-world settings (Hedley et al., 2017).

3.6.2 Adapting the Work Environment

Adapting the workplace environment is crucial to creating an inclusive and accessible space for people with autism. This may include physical modifications, such as reducing sensory input (lighting, noise, etc.), and adjustments to work routines and processes to accommodate individual needs (Myers et al., 2011).

Companies like SAP have implemented inclusion programs that include workplace adaptations such as quiet work areas and flexible work schedules. These adaptations help create

a more comfortable and productive environment for employees with autism, allowing them to perform their jobs effectively (Weiss; Roth, 2018).

Another effective practice is the implementation of assistive technologies that can support communication and task organization. Visual support software, digital reminders, and augmentative communication tools can be extremely useful for people with ASD, helping them carry out their daily activities at work (Gal; Sela, 2020).

3.6.3 Raising Awareness and Educating Colleagues and Employers

Raising awareness and educating colleagues and employers are essential components of promoting the inclusion of people with autism in the workplace. Training programs that address autism, its characteristics, and best practices for inclusion can help create a more understanding and welcoming workplace.

Awareness training can include workshops, seminars, and training sessions that teach about the challenges and strengths of people with ASD. These initiatives can demystify autism and reduce prejudice, promoting a culture of respect and inclusion (SCOTT et al., 2015).

Companies such as EY (Ernst & Young) have implemented training programs for their employees with the aim of raising awareness about autism and preparing staff to work effectively with colleagues with ASD. These programs help to build an inclusive corporate culture where all employees feel valued and supported (Hurlbutt; Chalmers, 2004).

3.7 Challenges and Future Perspectives

3.7.1 Current challenges in the inclusion of people with autism in the labor market

The inclusion of people with autism in the workplace faces several significant challenges. A lack of understanding and knowledge about autism among employers and coworkers can lead to bias and discrimination (Brugha et al., 2016). Furthermore, workplaces are often not adapted to meet the sensory and communication needs of people with autism, resulting in a stressful and exclusionary work environment (Hiller et al., 2014). A lack of support and specific training is also a significant obstacle, as many companies are not equipped to provide the necessary support for these individuals to perform their roles effectively (Hedley et al., 2018).

3.7.2 Trends and perspectives for the future

In the future, it is expected that there will be an increase in awareness and acceptance of autism in the workplace. Autism awareness and education initiatives can help reduce stigma and promote inclusion (Scott et al., 2019). Furthermore, implementing assistive technologies and adapting workplaces to be more accessible and inclusive can facilitate the inclusion of people with autism (Roux et al., 2015). Companies can begin to adopt more inclusive recruitment and selection practices that value the diversity and unique abilities of people with autism (Bagatell, 2010). Collaboration between companies, governments, and support organizations can result in more effective and inclusive employment policies and programs (Neville et al., 2016).

3.7.3 Recommendations for inclusive policies and practices

To promote the inclusion of people with autism in the job market, some recommendations include:

- **Education and awareness** : Implement autism training and awareness programs for employers and employees (Scott et al., 2019).
- **Adapting the work environment** : Modifying the work environment to be more accessible, taking into account the sensory and communication needs of people with autism (Hiller et al., 2014).
- **Support and mentoring** : Offer ongoing support and mentoring programs to help people with autism integrate and thrive in the workplace (Hedley et al., 2018).
- **Inclusive policies** : Develop and implement recruitment and selection policies that are inclusive and value diversity (Bagatell, 2010).
- **Partnerships and collaboration** : Establish partnerships between businesses, governments and support organizations to create inclusive and sustainable employment programs (Neville et al., 2016).

By adopting these recommendations, it is possible to create a more inclusive and equitable labor market, where people with autism can fully contribute their unique skills and talents.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

4.1 Conclusions

The research satisfactorily met the objective of answering the proposed problem questions, using the hypothetical-deductive method and a rigorous Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review. The five problem questions focused on identifying the barriers faced by people with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in the job market, effective strategies to promote their inclusion, the role of public policies, the economic and social impacts of inclusion, and the contribution of education and awareness in reducing stigma. The hypotheses were confirmed as the results showed that the barriers are multifaceted, including social, educational, and organizational aspects, and that effective strategies involve adapting the work environment, professional training programs, and raising awareness among employers and coworkers.

The main findings highlight that, although Brazilian legislation is robust in terms of rights guaranteed to people with disabilities, including those with ASD, the practical implementation of these laws still faces significant challenges. Specific training and capacity-building programs for people with autism, such as those implemented by large companies such as Microsoft and SAP, have proven to be effective in terms of inclusion, but are still limited in their scope. Gaps identified in the research include the need for greater adaptation in work environments and recruitment processes, as well as the lack of ongoing support and mentoring programs for these workers.

The theoretical contributions of the research include a deeper understanding of the interactions between the work environment and the specific needs of people with ASD, while the empirical contributions offer evidence of effective practices that can be replicated in different contexts. Methodologically, the research adds value by demonstrating how a Narrative Literature and Documentary Review can be used to address complex issues such as inclusion in the labor market. The added value to the topic is significant, especially with regard to raising awareness about the importance of inclusion in the labor market and developing more effective public policies. The research also contributes to the field of Science by advancing knowledge about inclusive practices and to society by proposing recommendations that can result in a more equitable and inclusive labor market.

4.2 Final Considerations

The theoretical implications of this research indicate the need for a reassessment of traditional approaches to inclusion, suggesting a greater focus on tailoring strategies to meet the unique needs of individuals with ASD. Empirically, the results point to the effectiveness of training and awareness programs, as well as the importance of adaptations in the workplace, which may influence future business practices. Methodologically, the research reinforces the relevance of Narrative Literature and Documentary Review as a powerful tool for compiling and analyzing data in areas where empirical research may be limited.

However, the research also has limitations. Theoretically, the reliance on secondary sources may limit the complete understanding of the variables involved in the inclusion of people with ASD in the labor market. Empirically, the variability in the quality of the studies analyzed, as well as the lack of longitudinal data, represents a significant limitation. Methodologically, the absence of field studies or direct empirical research limits the ability to validate the findings in real contexts.

For future research, it is suggested that longitudinal empirical studies be conducted that can follow the trajectory of people with ASD in the labor market, from their entry to their permanence and progression in their careers. In addition, the development of mixed methodologies, which combine qualitative and quantitative analysis, could offer a more robust view of the dynamics of inclusion. The creation of pilot programs in different sectors of the economy to test the practical recommendations identified in this research is also a promising area for future research. Such future research would not only fill the gaps identified, but also refine the methodologies employed, contributing to the construction of a truly inclusive labor market.

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